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Digital Clock

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Table of Contents

1	Aim of The Project.....	3
2	Abstract.....	3
3	Objective.....	4
4	Introduction	4
4.2	Explanation of block diagram.....	5
4.2	Features The main and significant features of this program.....	6
5	Design Ideas and Methods.....	7
5.1	Experimental Steps.....	7
5.2	Assembly Language Program.....	8
5.3	Requirement.....	11
5.4	Experimental Result.....	11
7	Summery.....	12
6	Conclusion.....	13
7	References.....	14
8	The Code Source of Digital Clock.....	15

Table of Figures

Figure No.

1	The block Diagram of digital clock.....	5
2	The flowchart of digital clock.....	6
3	Program for Digital clock function.....	8,9,10
4	The screen of Our Digital clock.....	11

Aim of the Project

To design and construct a digital clock using 8085 microprocessors program for real time of computer system

Abstract

This project utilizes the entirety of the information that we have learned all through the course. We went through the plan procedure, implemented gate logic, utilized flip-flops, structured counters, and put it all together. We additionally ran various tests to ensure each part was running accurately. There are basically two sorts of clocks. One being simple and the other being digital. The simple clock was the main kind of clock in the past when there was no computerized innovation accessible. Yet, with the beginning of digital period, computerized tickers have gotten one of our day by day necessities. We utilize digital clock in various structures like hand watch, mobile phones, PCs and so forth. We see digital clocks in our PCs consistently. It is a prime segment of these gadgets. In this task we have executed a digital clock utilizing the illustrations method of assembly language programming. Here we show how this should be possible and walk you through the entire procedure

Objective

- ✓ The objective of this experiment is to construct a digital clock in the lab using emulator LCD screen, emu8086 microprocessor emulator with integrated assembler.
- ✓ To be able to understand the principle behind digital system display
- ✓ To be able to display the data and time in 12 formats

Introduction

Assembly language is one the most punctual methods for PC programming. It is the most minimal degree of programming above machine language programming Assembly programming requires profound comprehension about the hardware we are managing. The hardware segments can be legitimately controlled utilizing this. Since the programmers can play with the segments as they wish, utilizing this programming strategy can get us free of a ton of repetition and hence make quicker projects. A digital clock is a kind of clock that shows the time carefully, rather than an analog clock, where the time is demonstrated by the places of pivoting hands. A clock is an instrument for estimating time. On a basic level, it requires close to some physical procedure which will continue at a known rate, and an approach to check to what extent that procedure has been proceeding. There are various sorts and sizes of clocks are accessible. Contingent upon the technique for time show, clocks can be classified by four kinds. They are i) analog clocks, ii) digital clocks, iii) auditory clocks, iv) textual clocks. Digital clocks are frequently connected with electronic drives; however, the "digital" depiction alludes just to the presentation, not the drive system. To represent to the time, most Digital clocks utilize a seven-fragment display. It shows hours, minutes and seconds and can be set to appear in both 24 hours and 12 hours format.

Explanation of block diagram

✚ **Figure1: The block Diagram of digital clock**

The above diagram simply shows how a digital clock works. The input is within the shape of electric alerts from the microprocessor. The electric indicator travel through the wires to the hardware of LCD display and intern travels to the screen of emulator LCD display as a result full digital clock appears on six different directions, but the sequence of the variations of the digits are different. For example first time measurement will starts which is seconds is displayed on the emu LCD screen as soon as the 60 seconds completes then second time measurements will starts which is minutes and after the completion of the 60 minutes the third time measurements starts which is hours, through this time measurement the full digital clock is displayed on the emu LCD screen. The input component represents the part wherein as mentioned above the electric indicator are transferred to the respective system, this is the part where after the wires are used to make all the respective connections in the LCD screen hardware with the wires, with the microprocessor and the power supply. The most important part of the input process is the part where the program is entered for the microprocessor. This will determine the process and the output of the whole system. Thus before the connections are made the microprocessor is programmed first for the digital clock to function in a correct manner.

Features The main and significant features of this program is described below.

1. The clock shows the time of the computer system.
2. It shows hours, minutes and seconds.
3. It uses 12-hour format.
4. The interface is simplistic with white text on black background.

The flowchart shows the process taking place inside a particular digital clock with the aid of step by step diagram. The flow chart gives a clearer and better idea of how a particular digital clock works and the makes it easier for one to understand. The following flowchart illustrates how a particular digital clock works.

Figure1: The flowchart of digital clock

Design Ideas and Methods

Through the top-down design method, the program can be divided into three major modules: Get time, printing time, and interrupt processing. After dividing the modules, the implementation and testing of each module can be implemented.

Experimental steps

From the above analysis, we can see that the experiment can be divided into three parts, so the experimental steps can be roughly divided into three parts.

1. Get Time
2. Print time
3. Interrupt handling

In the Get time module, we use the 2Ch instruction of int 21h to read the system time., Minutes and seconds are stored in CH, CL and DH registers respectively.

In the printing time module, we need to split the single digit and ten digits of the value to realize the printing of numeric characters, so we used the div instruction to find the quotient and the remainder of the value and 10. After getting the one-digit and ten-digit values, we print the numeric character data in the data segment line by line to achieve the display of hours, minutes and seconds. In the Interrupt handling module, we obtain the status of the keyboard buffer through the 01h instruction of int 16h, and then judge whether to End the program according to whether there is data in the buffer.

Assembly Language Program

The program was the main catalyst which makes the digital clock works. The program for the digital clock to work and the program for the delays are entered in order for the digital clock to work is the following:

LABEL	OPCODE	OPERAND	COMMENT
main_read_keyboard_buffer	mov	Ah,01h	keyboard that read time and buffer digits
	int	16h	
	jnz	exit	
main_load_time	mov	Ah,2ch	get current time
	int	21h	
	mov	Current_hour,ch	
	mov	Current_minute,cl	
	mov	Current_second,dh	
main_print_second	mov	Al,current_second	get current second to print out
	cmp	Second,al	
	jne	print	
main_print_minute	mov	Al,current_minute	get current minute to print out
	cmp	minute,al	
	jne	Print	
main_print_hour	mov	Al,current_hour	get current hour to print out
	cmp	Hour,al	
	jne	print	
	jmp	main	
print_update_hour	mov	Al,current_hour	print current updated hour
	mov	Hour,al	
print_update_minute	mov	Al,current_minute	print current updated minute
	mov	Minute,al	
print_update_second	mov	Al,current_second	print current updated second
	mov	Second,al	
print_clear_screen	call	clear_screen	display clear screen of current updated time
print_hour	mov	Al,current_hour	print hour
	mov	Time,al	
	call	Parse_time	analyzing time for current hour
	call	Set_digit	set digit for curent hour on screen
	mov	Column,1	
	call	Print_digit	display set digit of current hour on screen
	mov	Al,digit_unit	hour unit
	call	Set_digit	
	mov	Column,11	

	call	Print_digit	
Print_first_colon	mov	Al,0ah	
	call	Set_digit	
	mov	Column,21	
	call	Print_digit	display completed digit set of hour on screen
print_minute	mov	Al,current_minute	print minute
	mov	Time,al	
	call	Parse_time	analyzing time for current minute
	call	Set_digit	set digit for curent minute on screen
	mov	Column,31	
	call	Print_digit	display set digit of current minute on screen
	mov	Al,digit_unit	minute unit
	call	Set_digit	
	mov	Column,41	
	call	Print_digit	
Print_second_colon	mov	Al,0ah	
	call	Set_digit	
	mov	Column,51	
	call	Print_digit	display completed digit set of minutes on screen
print_second	mov	Al,current_second	print second
	mov	Time,al	
	call	Parse_time	analyzing time for current second
	call	Set_digit	set digit for current second on screen
	mov	Column,61	
	call	Print_digit	display set digit of current second on screen
	mov	Al,digit_unit	second unit
	call	Set_digit	
	mov	Column,71	
	call	Print_digit	display completed digit set of second on screen
	jmp	Main	
Parse_time	mov	Ah,0	parse time in "time", loading "digit_ten" and "digit_unit"
	mov	Al,time	
	mov	Bl,10	
	div	Bl	
	mov	Digit_ten,al	
	mov	Digit_unit,ah	
	ret		
Set_digit	mov	Bl,2	set digit from al to

			digit_pointer[si]
	mul	Bl	
	mov	Si,ax	
	mov	Si,digit_pointer[si]	
	ret		
Print_digit_reset	mov	Line,2	
	call	Set_cursor	display and placing cursor position to print digit rese
Print_digit_digit	mov	Dh,0	print digits one by one
	mov	DI,ds:[si]	
	cmp	Dx,"\$"	
	je	Print_digit_end	jump to set end digit
	cmp	Dx,10	
	je	Print_digit_new_line	jump to print out new line of digit
	mov	Ah,2	
	int	21h	
	inc	Si	
	jmp	Print_digit_digit	print each digit one by one
print_digit_new_line	inc	line	print out new current digits of time on screen
	call	Set_cursor	
	inc	Si	
	jmp	Print_digit_digit	
Print_digit_end	Ret		print out end of digits on screen
Set_cursor	mov	Ah,2	this will set cursor position on screen
	mov	Bh,page_number	
	mov	Dh,line	
	mov	DI,column	
	int	10h	
	ret		
Clear_screen	mov	Ah,0fh	get and set video mode
	int	10h	
	mov	Ah,0	
	int	10h	
	ret		
exit_clear_screen	call	Clear_screen	exit to display clear screen
exit_flush_keyboard_buffer	mov	Ah,0ch	exit to buffer full time on the screen
	mov	Ah,0	
	int	21h	
exit_signal	mov	Ax,4c00h	Exit to operating system.
	int	21h	

Figure2: Program for Digital clock function

Requirement

- For running the code, you have to use Emu8086.

Experimental results

After many experiments, the experiment code can display the system time (hours, minutes, and seconds), and at the same time can correctly respond to the End signal of the keyboard. The experiment results meet the requirements of the experiment. One of the test results is given below:

- ✚ **The output of current time of my computer system was 12:02:32.**

✚ Figure3: The screen of Our Digital clock

Summery

Overall, this trial was successful. After this trial, we can essentially master the basic strategies for x86 assembler design and be familiar with the utilization of emu8086 and visual studio tools. Since x86-related information has not been adapted methodically previously, we experienced a great deal of issues during the test. While executing the module of the keyboard interrupt program, we took a ton of detours. From the start, we needed to utilize the 25h guidance of int 21h to accomplish the normal capacity, however it was consistently ineffective. Afterward, rather than utilizing the 0Ah guidance of int 21h, we needed to understand the normal capacity by making a decision about the read buffer data, yet it was likewise fruitless. At long last, a few answers from Stack Overflow gave us some motivation. we judge whether the user has set off a keyboard event by judging whether there is data in the keyboard buffer in the main loop of the program, and afterward judge whether to interfere with the program.

During the time spent composing code, so as to make the improvement procedure clear, we have utilized an assortment of approaches to arrange the code, such as comments, blank lines, etc., and later found that it is a decent method to separate the code by methods for names and space the way. During the experiment, we felt that x86 contrasted with predominant MIPS, for example, register the executives and subroutine jumps, x86 gives an all the more friendly improvement technique. Yet, engineers despite everything need to focus on the administration of registers, to stay away from common contamination of registers. During the time spent beginning to build up the print digit sub-module, because of the absence of fastidious turn of events, we didn't see the contention between the one-digit and ten-digit enlists that put away the worth and the brief register of the sub-module, and there was an issue of unusual worth printing.

Conclusion

In conclusion it can be stated that the objective of the experiment was successfully achieved, as the digital clock works following the each time measurements. The programs for the whole digital clock was also entered successfully and as a result the clock is displayed on the emulator screen showing all time measurements from seconds to minutes and finally an hours, after the whole program was executed.

References

- <https://github.com/anindyaspaul/digital-clock-in-assembly/blob/master/src/DigitalClock.asm?fbclid=IwAR30MBlttSRnwri1cSZV74GSesEtQdKv3xXYJQmuMrEEJauU7UQR9N8hQp8>
- https://github.com/forughi/DigitalClock_8051_Assembly/blob/master/Clock.asm?fbclid=IwAR1Afu8vvfm3Zt--qGmabAzhdUDSrGDpdo-qQZ0nBefJXFY-sSOcP2oPyI4
- https://studentboxoffice.in/jntuh/notes/microprocessors-and-microcontrollers/program-for-digital-clock-design-using-8086/250?fbclid=IwAR0m8UKANI5_xG-TMbQysNvbQ03yyhnyTPgwZ9Ndr5tppuJ7f3MRglzn0uc

The code Source of Digital Clock

```

.stack 100h
.data
zero  db "  _  ", 10
      db " / _ \ ", 10
      db "| | | | ", 10
      db "| | | | ", 10
      db "| | | | ", 10
      db " \_ / ", 10, "$"

one   db "  _  ", 10
      db " / _ | ", 10
      db " | | | ", 10
      db " | | | ", 10
      db " | | | ", 10
      db " | _ | ", 10, "$"

two   db "  _  ", 10
      db " | _ \ ", 10
      db " ) | ", 10
      db " / / ", 10
      db " / /_ ", 10
      db " | _ | ", 10, "$"

three db "  _  ", 10
      db " | _ \ ", 10
      db " ) | ", 10
      db " | < ", 10
      db " ) | ", 10
      db " | _ / ", 10, "$"

four  db " _ _ ", 10
      db " | | | | ", 10
      db " | | | _ ", 10
      db " | _ | _ | ", 10
      db " | | | ", 10
      db " | _ | ", 10, "$"

five  db "  _  ", 10
      db " | _ | ", 10
      db " | _ ", 10
      db " | _ \ ", 10
      db " ) | ", 10
      db " | _ / ", 10, "$"

six   db "  _  ", 10
      db " / / ", 10
      db " / /_ ", 10
      db " | ' \ ", 10
      db " | ( ) | ", 10
      db " \_ / ", 10, "$"

seven db "  _  ", 10
      db " | _ | ", 10
      db " / / ", 10
      db " / / ", 10
      db " / / ", 10

```

```

            db " /_/" , 10, "$"
eight db "  ___ " , 10
            db " /_ \ " , 10
            db "| ( ) |" , 10
            db " >_ < " , 10
            db "| ( ) |" , 10
            db " \___/" , 10, "$"
nine  db "  ___ " , 10
            db " /_ \ " , 10
            db "| ( ) |" , 10
            db " \___/" , 10
            db " / / " , 10
            db " /_/" , 10, "$"
colon db "  " , 10
            db "  _ " , 10
            db " ( )" , 10
            db "  " , 10
            db "  _ " , 10
            db " ( )" , 10, "$"

line db 0
column db 6
page_number db 0
digit_unit db 0
digit_ten db 0
time db 0
    hour db 0
minute db 0
second db 0
    current_hour db 0
    current_minute db 0
    current_second db 0
digit_pointer dw 11 dup(?)
.code
    ; set segment registers
init:
    mov ax, data
    mov ds, ax
    mov digit_pointer[0], offset zero
    mov digit_pointer[2], offset one
    mov digit_pointer[4], offset two
    mov digit_pointer[6], offset three
    mov digit_pointer[8], offset four
    mov digit_pointer[10], offset five
    mov digit_pointer[12], offset six
    mov digit_pointer[14], offset seven
    mov digit_pointer[16], offset eight
    mov digit_pointer[18], offset nine
    mov digit_pointer[20], offset colon
    ;mov ah, 25h
    ;mov al, 23h
    ;mov dx, fim
    ;int 21h

main:
main__read_keyboard_buffer:    ;keyboard that read time and buffer digits
    mov ah, 01h
    int 16h
    jnz exit
main__load_time:    ; get current time
    mov ah, 2Ch

```

```

        int 21h
        mov    current_hour, ch
mov     current_minute, cl
mov     current_second, dh
main__print_second:    ; get current second to print out
mov     al, current_second
cmp     second, al
jne     print
main__print_minute:   ; get current minute to print out
mov     al, current_minute
cmp     minute, al
jne     print
main__print_hour:     ; get current hour to print out
        mov     al, current_hour
cmp     hour, al
jne     print
jmp     main
print:
    print__update_hour:                ;print current updated hour
        mov     al, current_hour
        mov     hour, al
    print__update_minute:              ;print current updated minute
mov     al, current_minute
mov     minute, al
    print__update_second:              ;print current updated second
mov     al, current_second
mov     second, al
    print__clear_screen:
        call    clear_screen            ;display clear screen of current
updated time
    print__hour:                        ; print hour
        mov     al, current_hour
mov     time, al
        call    parse_time              ;analyzing time for current hour
        call    set_digit               ;this will set digit for curent hour on screen
mov     column, 1
        call    print_digit             ;display set digit of current hour on screen
mov     al, digit_unit                  ;hour unit
        call    set_digit
mov     column, 11
        call    print_digit
    print__first_colon:
        mov     al, 0Ah
        call    set_digit
mov     column, 21
        call    print_digit            ;display completed digit set of hour on
screen
    print__minute:                      ;print minute
mov     al, current_minute
mov     time, al
        call    parse_time              ;analyzing time for current minute
        call    set_digit               ;this will set digit for curent minute on screen
mov     column, 31
        call    print_digit            ;display set digit of current minute on
screen
        mov     al, digit_unit          ;minute unit
        call    set_digit
mov     column, 41

```

```

        call print_digit
print__second_colon:
        mov al, 0Ah
        call set_digit
        mov column, 51
        call print_digit                ;display completed digit set of minutes
on screen
print__second:                ; print second
        mov al, current_second
        mov time, al
        call parse_time            ;analyzing time for current second
        call set_digit            ;this will set digit for current second on
screen
        mov column, 61
        call print_digit            ;display set digit of current second on
screen
        mov al, digit_unit        ;second unit
        call set_digit
        mov column, 71
        call print_digit            ;display completed digit set of second on
screen
        jmp main
parse_time:                ;parse time in "time", loading "digit_ten" and
"digit_unit"
        mov ah, 0
        mov al, time
        mov bl, 10
        div bl
        mov digit_ten, al
        mov digit_unit, ah
        ret
set_digit:                ; set digit from al to digit_pointer[si]
        mov bl, 2
        mul bl
        mov si, ax
        mov si, digit_pointer[si]
        ret
print_digit:                ;print digit in SI until find "$", set line = 2
and column = column
print_digit__reset:
        mov line, 2
        call set_cursor            ;display and placing cursor position to print
digit reset
print_digit__digit:        ;print digits one by one
        mov dh, 0
        mov dl, ds:[si]
        cmp dx, "$"
        je print_digit__end        ;jump to set end digit
        cmp dx, 10
        je print_digit__new_line    ;jump to print out new line of digit
        mov ah, 2
        int 21h
        inc si
        jmp print_digit__digit      ; it will print each digit one by one
print_digit__new_line:
        inc line                    ; print out new current digits of time on
screen
        call set_cursor

```

```

        inc si
        jmp print_digit_digit
print_digit_end:           ;print out end of digits on screen
        ret
set_cursor:                ;this will set cursor position on screen
        mov ah, 2
mov bh, page_number
mov dh, line
mov dl, column
int 10h
        ret
clear_screen:              ; get and set video mode
        mov ah, 0fh
int 10h
mov ah, 0
int 10h
        ret
exit:                       ;exit to display clear screen
exit_clear_screen:
        call clear_screen
exit_flush_keyboard_buffer: ;exit to buffer full time on the screen
        mov ah, 0Ch
        mov al, 0
        int 21h
exit_signal:
mov ax, 4C00h              ; exit to operating system.
int 21h
end init

```

